

A Case for Considering the Integration of Mentoring and a Learning Trajectory Framework to Support Educators' Professional Learning and Pedagogical Practice?

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High-quality early years education and care play an essential role in supporting young children's development, particularly those experiencing economic, emotional, or social challenges. National and international research highlights the significant impact of Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC) educators on children's development. In Ireland, the ECEC sector has witnessed an increasing emphasis on professional learning, as outlined in the Síolta Quality Framework (Standard 11), Aistear, the national curriculum framework, and in recent Government policies. Mentoring is internationally acknowledged as a key support in ensuring process quality in ECEC settings. This is acknowledged nationally, with settings having access to the Better Start National Early Years Quality Development Service, which supports the development of professional learning and practice through a mentoring programme. However, the impact of this programme is inconclusive, with recent data highlighting positive outcomes for specific areas or goals in a particular setting, but failing to influence the entire setting, and providing little evidence of sustained improvement. This may be attributed to the practice of self-reporting on outcomes and no measurable approach used. This paper explores the rationale for combining a mentoring programme with the Zone of Proximal Teacher Development (ZPTD) framework to support ECEC professional learning and pedagogical practice. This framework emphasises the dynamic interplay between prior experience and new knowledge, aligning with Vygotsky's principles of mediated learning. It defines four stages of development that provide a structured yet flexible, iterative foundation for professional growth.

Keywords: Early Childhood Education, Professional Learning, Mentoring, Constructivist, Zone of Proximal Teacher Development

Highlights

- **Ongoing professional learning is foundational to improving the quality of ECEC:** enhancing educators' pedagogical knowledge, supporting reflective practice, and strengthening their ability to provide high-quality, responsive interactions that promote positive child outcomes.
- **Mentoring has emerged as an established strategy for supporting professional learning:** Consideration of socio-cultural models that support co-construction between mentor and mentee, and not a transmissive approach.
- **Reframing mentoring through the Zone of Proximal Teacher Development (ZPTD) model** enables a more dynamic and tailored approach to educator learning, aligning support with individual developmental stages and contextual realities to promote sustained pedagogical improvement.

Introduction

High-quality early childhood education and care (ECEC) is widely recognised as a key contributor to positive lifelong outcomes for children (Phair, 2021). The benefits are well-documented, influencing cognitive, social, and emotional development well into adulthood (Melhuish et al., 2016; Heckman and Karapakula, 2019). These impacts are especially significant for children from socio-economically disadvantaged backgrounds, where quality ECEC can help bridge developmental and educational gaps (Siraj-Blatchford et al., 2008). Early years educators are the cornerstone of quality provision, and their learning and development significantly influence positive outcomes for children (Urban et al., 2011).

Research has consistently demonstrated that professional learning (PL) for early childhood educators enhances the quality of teaching (Pianta et al., 2008). Additionally, PL can bring about sustained, transformative changes to educators' practice, and can lead to improved children's outcomes in the long term (Walters et al., 2020). Despite its critical importance, professional learning (PL) for early childhood educators nationally remains fragmented and inconsistently implemented across diverse contexts (GOI, 2021). Among the strategies available to support educator development, mentoring has emerged as a particularly effective approach for enhancing pedagogical knowledge and fostering reflective practice (OECD, 2020; NCCA, 2013). However, there remains a pressing need to better understand how to embed and sustain high-quality professional learning, through mentoring, to drive improvements in early childhood education and care (ECEC), support educator development, and ultimately improve outcomes for children (Eadie et al., 2024).

In Ireland, the national mentoring programme, offered through The Better Start National Early Years Quality Development Service (QDS), established by the Department of Children and Youth Affairs in 2014, adopts a voluntary, strength-based, and whole-of-ECEC setting approach (O'Connor et al., 2020). A 2024 review (DCEDIY, 2024) highlighted the programme's strengths and limitations, with one key feature being the QDS's limited reach and issues regarding its suitability for the sector as a whole. The report suggests that further research is needed to determine who benefits most from the QDS and whether the programme is more effective for certain service types than others.

In light of these data, this essay will discuss an alternative approach to supporting early years educators' professional learning and pedagogical practice by integrating mentoring within a structured learning trajectory framework. The author proposes the *Zone of*

Proximal Teacher Development (ZPTD) (Warford, 2011) as a conceptual model for understanding and supporting educator learning through mentoring. By applying this framework, mentoring can be reconceptualised as a dynamic and developmentally responsive process that aligns with educators' evolving professional capacities and contextual needs.

The discussion will establish the importance of professional learning and highlight current challenges and the evolution of PL in Ireland. Similarly, the role of mentoring in supporting educator PL and the current national landscape will be presented. The ZPTD framework will be considered as an option to support and nurture professional learning and sustained improvement in pedagogical practice. The impact on pedagogical practice will not be presented here due to word count limitations. Its inclusion in the title underscores the need to use this as an outcome measure of effectiveness.

Debates in the literature highlight persistent ambiguity around the terms *professional learning (PL)*, *professional development (PD)* and *continuous professional development (CPD)*, which are often used interchangeably despite representing different emphases and traditions (Boylan et al., 2018; Mockler, 2022; King et al., 2023). This essay adopts Boylan et al.'s (2023) definition of PL, viewing it simultaneously as a process and an outcome, one that not only provides structured opportunities for learning but also leads to genuine shifts in educators' thinking and practice. For the purposes of this paper, professional learning is examined specifically within the Irish Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) system, while also drawing on international evidence to contextualise national strengths, limitations, and future opportunities.

Professional Learning (PL)

Conventional professional learning (PL) formats, particularly one-off workshops and formal training sessions, have long operated on a linear, transmission-based model of teacher development (Peleman, 2018). These approaches are increasingly criticised for producing limited, short-lived impacts on educators' practice and for overlooking the relational, situated, and evolving nature of professional learning (Opfer & Pedder, 2011; Sims & Fletcher-Wood, 2021). Their tendency to oversimplify the complexity of professional growth (Webster-Wright, 2017) undermines their effectiveness. As Schachter (date) argues, sustainable improvement requires PL designs that address teachers' skills, knowledge, and

dispositions together; weakening any one of these dimensions reduces the likelihood that new learning will be meaningfully enacted in practice.

In contrast, contemporary research conceptualises high-quality PL as collaborative, dynamic, and embedded in educators' everyday work (Boylan, 2021; Darling-Hammond, 2017). Within early childhood education and care (ECEC), this shift is reflected in growing support for holistic, teacher-centred, and context-responsive PL models (Liu et al., 2024). Korthagen (2017) highlights the centrality of educators' personal motivations—including their beliefs, emotions, and aspirations—arguing that these internal drivers shape how they interpret and apply new learning. This aligns with values-led frameworks that foreground reflection, meaning-making, and identity development (Kennedy, 2016; Liou & Carrinus, 2020; McChesney, 2022). Such approaches help educators strengthen their sense of professional purpose and respond more confidently to the complexity of contemporary educational settings (Mockler, 2022; Boylan et al., 2018). While international scholarship offers broad insights into effective PL design, these findings must be interpreted within the distinct policy, workforce, and qualification structures of the Irish ECCE sector.

Sustained programmes, unfolding over time and supported through cycles of practice, reflection, and refinement, are consistently linked with deeper and more lasting improvements (Guskey, 2002; Kennedy, 2016; Boylan et al., 2018). Peleman et al. (2018) stress that when PL becomes embedded in routine pedagogical and organisational structures, supported by coaching, inquiry, and follow-up, shifts in practice are more likely to endure. Organisational supports such as professional learning communities (PLCs) create shared spaces for observation, dialogue, and collective problem-solving (Admiraal, 2021), signalling that PL is a collective responsibility rather than an isolated activity. Researchers argue that the effectiveness of PL should ultimately be judged by demonstrable changes in practice and outcomes for children, rather than fidelity to programme delivery (Egert et al.; Schachter).

Collaboration is repeatedly identified as a catalyst for deep learning. Kennedy (2014) notes that collaborative inquiry enhances educator agency and supports the co-construction of pedagogical knowledge, while Baumfield et al. (2023) show that cross-professional collaboration can broaden perspectives and enrich problem-solving. Additionally, reflection within these collaborative environments enables the reconsideration of assumptions about children's learning, often prompting shifts in belief that precede behavioural change (Boylan et al., 2018). Personal dimensions of learning are equally important. Korthagen (2017) emphasises that cognitive, emotional, and motivational factors are intertwined in teacher

learning, and tools such as reflective logbooks or portfolios can help surface tacit processes that shape practice. Programmes grounded in real practice and embedded in daily routines, supported through coaching and ongoing inquiry, are therefore most likely to produce sustained change (Opfer & Pedder, 2011; Boylan, 2023).

In Ireland, these insights are increasingly relevant. Despite policy recognition of the importance of PL, access remains uneven and participation voluntary (OECD, 2021; DCEDIY, 2021; European Education and Culture Executive Agency, 2025), in contrast to systems where ongoing PL is a core professional obligation (Zepeda, 2019). The wide variation in qualifications across the early years workforce (DCEDIY, 2016) underscores the need for sustained, high-quality, and accessible PL opportunities. Importantly, evidence shows that the impact of PL is not determined by educators' initial qualifications (Egert et al., 2018; Eckhardt & Egert, 2020), reinforcing the potential of well-designed PL to enhance practice across the sector.

The evolution of PL in Ireland

The development of professional learning (PL) within Ireland's ECEC sector has been guided by several significant policy initiatives focused on enhancing quality, curriculum delivery, and the professionalisation of the workforce. The first of these, *Siolta*, which means "seed" in Irish, was launched in 2006 as the country's inaugural national quality framework for early years settings (DES, 2017). This was followed in 2009 by *Aistear*, meaning "journey", introduced by the National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA), establishing Ireland's national curriculum framework for children from birth to six years (NCCA, 2009). A comprehensive review of *Aistear* was completed, and an updated version was released in 2024 (NCCA, 2024). Both *Siolta* and *Aistear* emphasise the important role of ongoing professional learning in delivering high-quality early years education, and are applicable to all environments where children aged 0–6 are present.

The link between PL and quality enhancement was first formalised through *Siolta* with the introduction of the *Siolta Quality Assurance Programme* (QAP) in 2008 (DES, 2013). This structured initiative aimed to support both internal self-assessment and external evaluation, using defined quality indicators from the *Siolta* framework. The QAP sought to promote continuous, self-driven improvement among ECEC professionals by offering initial mentoring, followed by reflective self-evaluation processes (DCEDIY, 2013). However, the

programme's impact was limited by the lack of a coordinated national strategy, the optional nature of participation, and a group-based mentoring model that did not adequately address the unique needs of individual settings (DES, 2013).

Like *Siolta*, *Aistear* is not underpinned by legislation. While the framework was initially welcomed for its potential to enhance educational practice (French, 2013), its overall impact has been weakened by the lack of a coordinated, sector-wide implementation strategy, an issue that remains unaddressed (Woods, Mannion, & Garrity, 2022). The absence of a national plan has made it challenging to monitor consistent implementation, a concern noted by the OECD (2021), which also highlighted inadequate support and resources for educators (DES, 2013). In response, the 2024 revision of *Aistear* places greater emphasis on structured, ongoing professional learning as a means of achieving more cohesive curriculum implementation across the early years sector (NCCA, 2024).

The *First 5: A Whole-of-Government Strategy for Babies, Young Children and their Families 2019–2028* (GOI, 2018) represents a key government initiative aimed at improving professional learning for early childhood educators through comprehensive policy reform. A major goal of the strategy is to establish a unified quality framework to support improvements across the ECEC system. *First 5* specifically highlights the importance of providing educators with the knowledge and skills needed to meet the evolving requirements of their roles, thereby positioning PL as a foundational element of workforce development in early childhood education (GOI, 2018).

Building on *First 5*, the *Nurturing Skills: Workforce Plan for Early Learning and Care and School-Age Childcare 2022–2028* (DCEDIY, 2021) was introduced to develop a well-qualified, professional, and adequately supported ECEC and school-age childcare workforce. This plan prioritises enhanced career pathways, improved qualifications, and increased access to professional learning. Pillar 3 of the plan focuses on creating a national PL system that includes both formal and informal learning opportunities. This reflects international research supporting the effectiveness of context-rich PL, which integrates pedagogical theory, peer collaboration, and supervisory support (Peleman et al., 2018). The development of a national PL system was intended to begin with the establishment of an oversight group to guide the implementation of several commitments in Pillar 3 of *Nurturing Skills* (GOI, 2024). No formal update is available on progress.

Despite this, overall Professional learning in Ireland's ECEC sector has evolved. It continues to grow through successive national frameworks and strategies—*Síolta*, *Aistear*, *First 5*, and *Nurturing Skills*—all emphasising the importance of structured, ongoing professional learning. Within this, Mentoring has emerged as a recommended approach for enhancing pedagogical knowledge and fostering reflective practice (OECD, 2020; NCCA, 2013).

Mentoring

Internationally, mentoring is widely recognised as a key predictor of high-quality educator–child interactions, contributing significantly to improved learning outcomes for children (OECD, 2021), and a key component of professional learning in educator development (Hobson et al, 2009). Mentoring is about drawing out, learning, and development, rather than merely reaching a predetermined goal and achieving definable competencies (Tonna et al., 2017). Chambers et al. (2015, p.2) offered that mentorship is a “profession-building endeavour as mentors and mentees are co-learners on a voyage of discovery”. Mentoring should offer not only a support mechanism but also a transformative process that fosters reflection, resilience, and sustained professional growth (Philips et al., 2016; Stanulis et al., 2019).

Traditional models, such as apprenticeship-style or directive mentoring, often reflect a hierarchical, transmissive approach in which the mentor is positioned as the expert and the mentee as a passive recipient of knowledge (Heikkinen et al., 2012), underpinned by a power imbalance (Tonna et al., 2017). Contemporary mentoring models have evolved from this 'transmission orientation' approach to 'professional responsibility' over time (Glover et al., 2024), repositioning the mentee as an active participant in the learning process (Larsen et al., 2023). Rather than instructing or directing, the mentor acts as a co-learner, fostering growth-producing experiences based on mutual trust and shared inquiry (Tuyan, 2023).

Mirroring the features of effective PL programmes presented previously, the most effective mentoring practices are those that are sustained over time and meaningfully integrated into everyday professional practice, rather than imposed externally or limited to short-term interventions (Nolan & Molla, 2018). Aligning with educators' professional values, promoting autonomy and self-directed learning (Kennedy, 2016; Korthagen, 2017; Mockler, 2022). Context-specific mentoring, in particular, supports the development of

pedagogical skills and professional identity through dialogic and socially situated learning processes (Kyndt et al., 2016; Walters et al., 2019). Key elements of effective mentoring include structured feedback, guided observation, collaborative goal setting, purposeful planning, and opportunities for critical reflection (Elek & Page, 2019; Glover et al., 2024). As Tuyan (2023) argues, knowing what occurs in the classroom is not sufficient to become an effective educator; understanding the *whys* and *what-ifs* behind pedagogical decisions is far more critical. This deeper understanding emerges through the sustained practice of reflective thinking, which involves self-evaluation, self-monitoring, and self-observation (Tuyan, 2023). Reflective practice is enacted when educators critically examine both their own theories and those of others, and when they modify, refine, or replace these theories in response to tensions, contradictions, or ineffectiveness (Tonna et al., 2017). As Nolan (2017) emphasises, reflection is not only an individual pursuit but also a collective endeavour that contributes to the development of shared professional knowledge and practice.

Moreover, mentoring should be sensitive to socio-political contexts and designed to support educators' unique needs (Brownlee et al., 2011). Mentoring, when viewed as a social practice, recognises the interplay between an individual's subjective meaning-making systems and the objective structures within which they operate (Nolan & Molla, 2018). The importance of understanding educators' epistemological beliefs to gain insight into their thinking, actions, and influence offers the mentor an opportunity to tailor supports and information relative to their beliefs, which are influenced by prior learning and experience (Brownlee et al. 2011; Nolan 2017).

National Mentoring Programme

Better Start Quality Development Service (QDS) was launched in 2014 (DCYA, 2014). The service was created to streamline and coordinate government-funded quality support systems for Early Learning and Care (ELC) settings, with the primary aim of ensuring consistent, high-quality practices that support positive developmental outcomes for children. Guided by the national frameworks *Siolta* and *Aistear*, Better Start offers customised mentoring and coaching to ELC providers. This support is designed to cultivate reflective, high-quality practices among educators and to equip them with the knowledge, competencies, and tools needed to promote holistic development and create rich, supportive learning environments (O'Connor et al, 2020).

The QDS model draws on principles from mentoring theory, child development, adult learning, and strengths-based methodologies. It facilitates the implementation of the Aistear-Síolta Practice Guide (ASPG), which serves as a key resource for aligning educational practice with national standards. Early Years Specialists (EYSs) deliver support in multiple formats, including in-person visits, online mentoring, coaching, training sessions, and ongoing communication via phone and email. Providers are also directed to additional resources for continued learning and development.

Better Start QDS Mentoring Model

1. Introduction & Relationship Building

The Early Years Specialist (EYS) introduces the QDS process to staff, clarifies roles, and establishes a collaborative foundation. A Quality Lead Person (QLP) may be nominated, and initial focus areas are discussed.

2. Observations & Feedback

Observation of daily practice to identify strengths and areas for development. Using structured tools informed by the Aistear Síolta Practice Guide (ASPG) Pillars, this phase ensures transparent, consistent feedback.

3. Joint Assessment & Goal Setting

In partnership with educators and the QLP, the EYS supports the assessment of current practices. Quality goals are agreed upon through self-evaluations, observations, and reflections. This is a dynamic and evolving process.

4. Implementation & Strategies

The EYS applies tailored mentoring and coaching strategies—guided by a strengths-based approach—to help educators implement and refine their quality goals in practice.

5. Review & Consolidation

Before concluding support, the team reviews progress, outcomes for children, and the impact of implemented actions. Final recommendations are agreed upon to ensure continued quality development.

The Better Start Quality Development Service (QDS), while associated with reported improvements in Early Learning and Care (ELC) settings, presents several limitations that warrant critical examination. The 2024 evaluation covering 2015–2023 (DCEDIY, 2024)

highlights concerns about the sustainability, depth, and diffusion of quality improvements achieved through QDS engagement. Much of the evidence for impact is self-reported and therefore vulnerable to bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003), with independent assessments suggesting that improvements are often modest and not consistently embedded across entire settings. The programme's targeted, strengths-based approach, though valued for its flexibility, may limit its systemic impact, particularly in environments with high staff turnover (DCEDIY, 2024). The review also highlights that many changes resulted in targeted outcomes in specific rooms rather than whole-setting improvements. Some national stakeholders question whether the QDS is delivering comprehensive, long-term change or merely fragmented, short-term gains, underscoring the need for further research into its scalability, appropriateness, and impact across diverse service types (DCEDIY, 2024). One significant absence is the lack of data on the impact on children, whilst a feature of the model this data was not gathered.

Theoretical Foundations

The theoretical foundations of mentoring are strongly informed by constructivist and sociocultural learning theories (Castanheira, 2016). Constructivist models emphasise collaborative dialogue, shared agency, and the integration of prior knowledge, beliefs, and experiences into the construction of new professional understandings (Tonna et al., 2017). Within this framework, learning is not a unidirectional transmission from mentor to mentee, but a reciprocal, co-constructed process facilitated through dialogue, reflection, and mutual engagement (Walters et al., 2020; Tonna et al., 2017). Mentoring thus becomes a partnership, rather than a hierarchical relationship. These theoretical perspectives challenge traditional, top-down models of professional development by positioning mentoring as a collaborative, experiential, and socially mediated practice. Knowledge is actively shaped through participation, interaction, and contextualised experiences, aligning closely with the practical realities of early years education (Castanheira, 2016).

Vygotsky's ZPD and Mentoring in Educator Learning

Mentoring can be understood through Vygotsky's sociocultural theory, specifically the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), the gap between what a learner can achieve independently and what they can accomplish with support (Vygotsky, 1978). Providing a

valuable framework for understanding educator learning as a socially mediated, co-constructed process shaped by tools, language, and interaction (Shabani, 2016; Eun, 2019).

Vygotsky (1979) emphasised development as inherently social—learning moves from shared (intermental) to individual (intramental) processes through purposeful collaboration (Eun, 2019; Shabani, 2016). Wass and Golding (2014) highlight the importance of scaffolding tasks beyond a learner’s current ability, stimulating cognitive challenge and promoting growth, thereby sustaining a constantly evolving learning zone. They further illustrate how scientific and everyday concepts evolve within the ZPD: everyday knowledge becomes more conscious and structured, while scientific understanding is enriched by personal experience. This interplay defines the ZPD as a space where theoretical and practical understanding merge, making it central to mentoring and professional learning (Shabani, 2016).

Application to Educator Development

Extending Vygotsky’s concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) to teacher education, Warford (2011) introduces the Zone of Proximal Teacher Development (ZPTD). Warford’s (2011) four-stage framework — self-assistance, teacher assistance, internalisation, and recurrence — maps a trajectory from scaffolded learning to independent professional growth. This model adapts Vygotskian theory to adult learners, recognising that teacher development builds on pre-existing professional knowledge and beliefs and the importance of establishing this through reflective practice.

Warford suggests that, unlike the traditional ZPD for children, in the Zone of Proximal Teaching Development (ZPTD), the initial stages are reversed: teacher candidates begin with self-assistance, engaging in reflection on prior experiences, beliefs, and tacit knowledge. This reversal acknowledges that adult learners bring existing cognitive and experiential resources to the mentoring process (Brownlee, 2011). The distinction between self- and teacher-assistance in this framework is not binary but emphatic; at early stages, the emphasis is on promoting reflective inquiry rather than direct instruction. While some guidance from mentors or teacher educators may remain, the focus is on creating space for educators to critically explore their own understandings before more structured forms of support are introduced. The importance of this initial tuning in phase cannot be overstated; the mentor cannot hope to produce educator leaning without carefully calibrating their pedagogical dispositions (Shabani, 2016). This perspective aligns with the arguments

presented by Brownlee (2011) and Nolan (2017), who emphasise the centrality of epistemological beliefs as the foundation for ongoing professional learning and pedagogical transformation. The development and evolution of these beliefs have the potential to drive deep and lasting professional change (Brownlee, 2011; Feucht, 2017). In a similar vein, Warford (2011) advocates for bringing educators' tacit assumptions into critical awareness and actively integrating them into new pedagogical approaches, allowing them to interweave expert and experiential knowledge into coherent personal narratives.

Warford's (2011) *Zone of Proximal Teacher Development* (ZPTD) aligns closely with the recognised features of effective professional learning. Core principles, such as sustained and iterative development, inquiry-based reflection, and practice-embedded learning, are reflected in ZPTD's staged structure. The model begins with *self-assistance*, encouraging teacher candidates to critically reflect on their prior knowledge and beliefs, a clear nod to inquiry-oriented, learner-driven development (Timperley et al., 2007; Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). As candidates progress to *teacher assistance*, *internalisation*, and *recurrence*, they engage in ongoing cycles of feedback, application, and personal meaning-making, consistent with transformative and situated models of professional learning (Feucht, 2017). Building directly on the characteristics of effective PL outlined above, ZPTD offers a developmental lens that can structure and support the kinds of reflective, sustained, practice-embedded learning that Irish and international research identify as most impactful.

Similarly, the core features of effective mentoring are reflected in ZPTD's relational and developmental orientation. Warford (2011) places value on adult learners' prior knowledge, emphasising non-hierarchical mentoring that fosters critical reflection rather than directive teaching. This aligns with mentoring approaches that emphasise epistemological growth and learner autonomy (Brownlee, 2011; Nolan and Molla, 2018). By situating professional growth within the candidates' belief systems and encouraging mentors to guide rather than instruct, ZPTD resists dominant transmission models. Instead, it positions mentoring as a dialogic and identity-shaping process, one that enables deep epistemological change and supports the development of reflective, adaptive practitioners.

Limitations of Using Mentoring in Combination with the ZPTD Framework

While the integration of mentoring and Warford's (2011) *Zone of Proximal Teacher Development* (ZPTD) offers a theoretically rich approach to supporting and assessing

educator learning, several limitations must be acknowledged when applying this framework in research and practice.

Firstly, the abstract and developmental nature of ZPTD poses challenges in operationalisation. The model's four stages—*self-assistance*, *teacher assistance*, *internalisation*, and *recurrence*—are conceptually nuanced and often fluid in practice. Identifying discrete transitions between stages can be difficult, potentially undermining the consistency and clarity of data collection and analysis. Furthermore, ZPTD is deeply embedded in educators' internal processes—such as reflection, prior experience, and tacit knowledge—making professional growth inherently subjective and complex to measure with reliability (Tonna et al., 2017; Korthagen, 2017; Brownlee et al., 2011).

Additionally, mentoring itself is not a uniform intervention. Its effectiveness depends on the mentor's skills, style, and relational dynamics, as well as the specific context of the ECEC setting. These variables can lead to inconsistent implementation and may affect the fidelity and comparability of research findings across different settings (Elek and Page, 2018; Glover et al., 2024; Larsen et al., 2023). Another limitation concerns the data-collection demands of a ZPTD-informed mentoring study. Capturing educators' development through this lens would require rich qualitative data—such as narrative reflections, interviews, and direct observations—which can be resource-intensive and time-consuming (Mockler, 2022; Nolan and Molla, 2018). This may be particularly challenging in under-resourced or high-turnover settings, where sustained engagement over time is difficult to maintain (DCEDIY, 2024).

Contextual factors further complicate research outcomes. Numerous external elements, including organisational culture, leadership, workload, and policy constraints, influence educator learning. These factors may mediate or obscure the specific effects of mentoring and the ZPTD framework, making it difficult to attribute observed changes solely to the intervention (Boylan et al., 2018; DCEDIY, 2024).

Lastly, the personalised and context-specific nature of ZPTD-based mentoring, while a strength in practice, limits the generalisability of findings. As the framework tailors support to individual developmental trajectories, it may not scale easily or produce outcomes applicable across varied service types or national contexts. Moreover, given the limited empirical research on ZPTD in early childhood settings, researchers may face difficulties identifying validated instruments or established methodologies (Warford, 2011). While the

ZPTD framework provides a compelling conceptual structure for mentoring and professional growth, its implementation in research requires careful attention to methodological rigour, contextual sensitivity, and practical feasibility.

Conclusion

High-quality professional learning (PL) remains essential to strengthening pedagogical practice across Ireland's ECEC sector, where educators' knowledge, dispositions, and interactions directly shape children's learning experiences and developmental trajectories (Boylan et al. 2023; Schachter 2015). International data demonstrate that sustained, practice-embedded PL is strongly associated with improved instructional quality, richer adult-child interactions, and enhanced outcomes in language, socio-emotional development, and cognition (Darling-Hammond et al. 2017; Egert, Fukkink and Eckhardt 2018; Eurofound, 2015). Irish research echoes these findings, with national evaluations showing that when educators access consistent, high-quality PL, settings demonstrate higher levels of process quality, more intentional pedagogical decision-making, and more responsive interactions with children (Urban et al. 2017).

Despite this, national policy frameworks such as *Síolta* (CECDE 2006), *Aistear* (NCCA 2024), *First 5* (GOI, 2018) and *Nurturing Skills* (DCEDIY 2022) acknowledge that PL remains uneven and insufficiently embedded across the sector, contributing to persistent variability in the quality of children's day-to-day experiences (DCEDIY, 2021). Consequently, strengthening the coherence, accessibility, and effectiveness of PL is vital not only for supporting educator development but also for ensuring equitable outcomes for children.

Mentoring is widely recognised, both nationally and internationally, as a powerful mechanism for supporting educator learning—particularly when it promotes reflection, collaboration, and inquiry rather than transmissive, compliance-oriented approaches (Castanheira, 2016). However, national evaluations of the *Better Start Quality Development Service* indicate that existing mentoring structures have not consistently achieved sustainable, whole-setting pedagogical change, with outcomes often limited to specific rooms, individuals, or short-term goals (DCEDIY 2021). These limitations highlight the need for a more robust, theoretically grounded model to guide and structure professional growth (Opfer & Pedder, 2011; Webster-Wright, 2017).

Integrating mentoring with *Warford's Zone of Proximal Teacher Development (ZPTD)* offers a promising pathway forward. ZPTD positions educator learning as an iterative, socially mediated process rooted in prior experience and evolving professional identity (Warford 2011). Its emphasis on scaffolded support, reflective meaning-making, and gradual internalisation aligns with international evidence on effective PL (Darling-Hammond et al. 2017; Egert et al. 2018). In mentoring, ZPTD provides a clearer developmental trajectory, enabling mentors to calibrate support while fostering deeper pedagogical stretch (Boylan 2021; Sims & Fletcher-Wood 2021). This integration has the potential to shift mentoring from episodic assistance to a more sustained and transformative form of PL.

While challenges remain—including the complexity of assessing reflective and epistemic change and the contextual variability of mentoring practices across Ireland (Urban et al. 2017)—the combined model offers a compelling framework for strengthening the emerging national PL system. Further research is needed to explore its feasibility, scalability, and impact on both educator practice and child outcomes, ensuring that mentoring can fulfil its potential as a cornerstone of high-quality PL.

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